

EFFECTS OF ULTRASONIC TREATMENT ON MICROSTRUCTURE AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF HYBRID PARTICULATES REINFORCED AL-ALLOY MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The effects of ultrasonic treatment (UT) on the microstructure and mechanical properties of 10 wt.% Mg₂Si+1 wt.% nano-sized SiC particles (SiC_{np} for short) hybrid reinforced Al-Cu alloy matrix composites were investigated for the first time. The results show that after UT, the big eutectic Mg₂Si phase was remarkably refined, from coarse Chinese characters (about 50 μm) to fine strips or dots (about 0.5~2 μm). Meanwhile SiC_{np} agglomerations were also eliminated, and both Mg₂Si phase and SiC_{np} were uniformly distributed in the composites. The as-cast ultimate tensile strength (UTS) and elongation of hybrid Mg₂Si+SiC_{np}/Al-Cu composites fabricated by combining UT and squeeze casting (SC) were enhanced to 336 MPa and 3.0%, which were increased by 31.3% and 130.8%, respectively, compared with the composites without UT. The UTS of the hybrid Mg₂Si+SiC_{np}/Al-Cu composites was also 33.5% higher than that of the Al-Cu matrix alloy and 23.5% higher than that of 1wt.% SiC_{np}/Al-Cu composites prepared by the same process.

1 INTRODUCTION

Particles reinforced aluminum matrix composites (PAMCs) have attracted more and more attention in the aerospace, military and automotive industries due to their excellent performances such as light weight, high specific strength and good wear resistance [1]. Mg₂Si is one kind of excellent reinforcing particles because of its low density, high melting point and high elastic modulus, and it can be easily in-situ formed in Al alloys by ingot metallurgy with big weight fraction [2].

However, the as-cast Mg₂Si phase tends to be large in size and sharp-horn-shaped, which degrades the mechanical properties and limits the potential applications of Mg₂Si-containing materials. Therefore, in order to optimize the Mg₂Si morphology and properties of the in-situ Mg₂Si/Al composites, conventional methods such as modification treatment [3] or addition of alloying elements [4] were used. At present, a novel hybrid particulate reinforced aluminum matrix composites, containing Mg₂Si with the other particles such as AlP and TiB₂, have attracted a lot of interests [5]. However, few studies on the hypoeutectic Mg₂Si (Mg₂Si<13.9 wt.%) and SiC_{np} hybrid reinforced aluminum matrix composites have been reported so far.

SiC particles have excellent properties such as high strength, high wear resistance and low thermal expansion rate [6-7]. However, it is difficult to produce nano-SiC_p particles reinforced aluminum matrix composites with big weight fraction by liquid addition method due to its large specific surface area and poor wettability [8]. Therefore, it is expected that the hybridization of Mg₂Si and SiC_{np} could solve the problem of limited particle weight fraction, and improve the Mg₂Si morphology. However, in order to overcome the difficulties in the preparation of Mg₂Si and SiC_{np} hybrid reinforced composites, it is necessary to develop a simple and effective process.

Ultrasonic technology has broad application prospects in the field of aluminum matrix composites due to its advantages of environmental friendship, energy saving, low cost, simple operation and high efficiency [9-10]. When preparing PAMCs, the acoustic cavitation and streaming generated by UT can effectively promote the uniform dispersion of solute atoms and reinforcement particles. However, studies on the effects of UT on in-situ Mg₂Si and ex-situ SiC_{np} hybrid reinforced aluminum matrix composites have not been reported.

In this study, a process consisting of UT and squeeze casting was firstly proposed to prepare

$Mg_2Si+SiC_{np}/Al-Cu$ composites, which can effectively refine the in-situ Mg_2Si phase and promote the uniform distribution of SiC_{np} . The effects of UT on the microstructure and mechanical properties of $Mg_2Si+SiC_{np}/Al-Cu$ composites are discussed in detail.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The compositions of Al-Cu matrix alloy were 5 wt% Cu, 0.5 wt% Mn, 0.15 wt% Ti, 0.3 wt% Mg, 0.15 wt% Fe, and the remaining Al. Raw materials such as Al-10Mn, Al-5Ti-B, Al-20Si master alloys ingots, pure Al, Mg, Cu ingots, and mm-sized SiC_{np}/Al composite granules fabricated by ball milling method mentioned in author's previous study [7], were melted in a graphite crucible at 750 °C to prepare the 10 wt.% Mg_2Si+1 wt.% $SiC_{np}/Al-Cu$ composites. Then the mechanical stirring was carried out for 10 min at a speed of 150 rpm. After that, the high-purity argon was introduced into the melt for refining, and then the melt was poured into a preheated metal cup and transferred to the holding furnace. When the melt temperature dropped to 720 °C, the ultrasonic horn preheated for 5min at 600 °C was inserted into the melt and then UT was applied for 5 min with the power of 2.8 kW and frequency of 20 kHz, during which the temperature varied from 705 °C to 690 °C. The whole process was under the protection of Ar gas, as shown in Fig. 1(a). After UT, the melt was poured into a 200 °C preheated mold, with pouring temperature of 690 °C. Then the casting ingots with diameter of 30 mm and height of 100 mm were obtained by squeeze casting at a pressure of 50 MPa, as shown in Fig. 1(b).

The microstructure of the $Mg_2Si+SiC_{np}/Al-Cu$ composites was observed by an OM DMM-480C optical microscope and a JEOL JSM-7600F scanning electron microscope. The phase composition of the composites was analyzed using an Empyrean XRD with a scanning angle ranging from 20 ° to 90 ° and a scanning speed of 10 °/min. The mechanical properties of composites were tested using a SHIMADZU AG-IC100KN machine at a drawing speed of 1 mm/min, and the GB/T228.1-2010 standard was followed.

Fig. 1. Sketch of (a) ultrasonic treatment system and (b) squeeze casting process.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Effects of UT on microstructure of the composites

Fig. 2 shows the XRD patterns of $Mg_2Si+SiC_{np}/Al-Cu$ composites with UT and without UT. It can be seen that the main constituent phases of composites are $\alpha-Al$, Al_2Cu , Mg_2Si and SiC_{np} . No other impurity peaks like Si or Al_4C_3 are found, which indicates that Mg and Si atoms reacted completely in the melt to form Mg_2Si phase. It also suggests that SiC_{np} are successfully added to the melt and the interfacial reaction between SiC_{np} and Al liquid is well controlled. After UT, the peak intensity of the $\alpha-Al$, Al_2Cu , Mg_2Si and SiC phases in the composites does not change and no new phases are formed, which indicates the application of UT has no effect on the phase constituent of composites.

Fig. 3 shows optical microstructure of the $Mg_2Si+SiC_{np}/Al-Cu$ composites without and with UT. As shown in Fig. 3(a) and (b), the primary $\alpha-Al$ grains are refined by UT, the average size of primary $\alpha-Al$ grains decreases from 20 μm (without UT) to 12 μm (with UT). For the refinement of primary $\alpha-Al$ grains, there are two main reasons: (i) SiC_{np} are pushed to the front of solid/liquid interface during the solidification, which hinders the growth of primary $\alpha-Al$ grains, leading to grain refinement [10]; (ii) The acoustic cavitation and streaming generated by UT can also increase the number of nucleation,

promote nucleation and refine grains [10-11].

Fig. 2. XRD patterns of $Mg_2Si+SiC_{np}/Al-Cu$ composites: (a) UT, (b) Without UT.

Fig. 3. Optical microstructure of the $Mg_2Si+SiC_{np}/Al-Cu$ composites: (a) Without UT, (b) With UT.

Fig. 4 shows SEM images of the $Mg_2Si+SiC_{np}/Al-Cu$ composites without and with UT. As shown in Fig. 4(a), SiC_{np} agglomerations exist in the composites without UT. This is because SiC_{np} cannot be captured by $\alpha-Al$ during solidification and are pushed to the front of solid/liquid interface, and finally to the grain boundaries [10,12]. After UT, SiC_{np} were uniformly dispersed in the composites due to the effects of acoustic cavitation and streaming [10-11]. Besides the direct effects of UT on SiC_{np} , UT can also affect the morphology and distribution of the eutectic Mg_2Si . Without UT, the eutectic Mg_2Si phase is mainly dominated by coarse Chinese characters, and there are also some dot Mg_2Si phases with the diameter of about 1~3 μm , which are only distributed in the SiC_{np} agglomerations region, as shown in Fig. 4. This indicates that SiC_{np} may have a certain effect on the refinement of eutectic Mg_2Si phase. After UT, the eutectic Mg_2Si phase is remarkably refined, and almost all of the coarse Chinese characters become dot phases with the size of about 0.5~2 μm , which are uniformly precipitated throughout the alloy. This indicates that UT can significantly change the morphology of eutectic Mg_2Si phase and promote its uniform precipitation. This is because that UT can promote the uniform distribution of Mg and Si solute atoms in the melt due to the effects of acoustic cavitation and acoustic streaming generated by high-energy ultrasonic waves in melt [9].

In order to better observe the eutectic Mg_2Si regions dispersed in the composites without and with UT, a local higher magnification SEM observation is performed as shown in Fig. 5. The positions of holes are Mg_2Si because of etching effect of samples. Without UT, there are agglomerated nanoparticles inside and around the dot eutectic Mg_2Si phase in the composites, as shown in Fig. 5(a). The results of EDS show that these nanoparticles are SiC_{np} , as shown in Fig. 5(c)(d). After UT, the dispersed SiC_{np} are also distributed inside and around the core of the eutectic Mg_2Si phase, as shown in Fig. 5(b). It seems that the distribution of SiC_{np} affects the nucleation and growth of eutectic Mg_2Si

phase, reducing its size and improving its morphology. In order to discuss the mechanism of SiC_{np} on the nucleation and growth of eutectic Mg_2Si phase, the crystalline structures of Mg_2Si and SiC are analyzed. The Mg_2Si crystal is a typical face-centered cubic with a lattice constant of 6.39 Å [5]. SiC is also a face-centered cubic crystal structure with a lattice constant of 4.36 Å. Therefore, the coherent relationship between Mg_2Si and SiC can be measured by the lattice mismatch (Turnbull-Vonnegut formula) [13]. Table 1 represents several sets of coherent interfaces of Mg_2Si and SiC , which indicates that SiC_{np} can act as heterogeneous nucleus of Mg_2Si phase, or be captured by the Mg_2Si solid front during solidification, leading to the refinement of eutectic Mg_2Si phase.

Fig. 4. SEM images of the $\text{Mg}_2\text{Si}+\text{SiC}_{\text{np}}/\text{Al-Cu}$ composites: (a)(c) without UT, (b)(d) with UT.

Fig. 5. High magnification SEM images of $\text{Mg}_2\text{Si}+\text{SiC}_{\text{np}}/\text{Al-Cu}$ composites: (a) without UT, (b) with UT, (c) EDS of point A, (d) EDS of point B.

Table 1: The coherent interfaces of Mg₂Si and SiC($\delta < 5\%$).

Number	SiC (fcc)		Mg ₂ Si (fcc)		δ (%)
	d (nm)	(h k l)	d (nm)	(h k l)	
1	0.436	0 0 1	0.452	1 1 0	3.54
2	0.308	1 1 0	0.320	2 0 0	3.75
3	0.251	1 1 1	0.261	2 1 1	3.83
4	0.195	2 1 0	0.193	3 1 1	1.04
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3.2 Effects of UT on the mechanical properties of composites

Table 2 shows the mechanical properties of matrix alloy and different composites. Without UT, the UTS and elongation of the Mg₂Si+SiC_{np}/Al-Cu composites are only 286 MPa and 1.3%. According to Fig. 3, there are large SiC_{np} agglomerations in the composites without UT, where the cracks will initiate and propagate continuously when the composites are subjected to the applied load. Moreover, the coarse eutectic Mg₂Si phase will split the matrix to further degrade the mechanical properties. In contrast, the UTS and elongation of composites with UT are 336 MPa and 3.0%, which are increased by 17.5% and 130.8%, respectively, compared with the composites without UT. This improvement may result from the elimination of SiC_{np} agglomerations and the refined eutectic Mg₂Si phase due to the effects of acoustic cavitation and streaming generated by UT. Moreover, the UTS is 33.5% higher than that of the Al-Cu matrix alloy and 23.5% higher than that of 1 wt.% SiC_{np}/Al-Cu composites, but the elongation is significantly reduced, as shown in Table 2. This is mainly due to the brittleness of Mg₂Si phase in the present composites.

The UTS and elongation of the 10wt.% Mg₂Si+1wt.% SiC_{np}/Al-Cu composites are significantly improved after UT. For the improvement of the mechanical properties of composites with UT, except for the effects of α -Al grain refinement [14] and uniform distribution of SiC_{np} [15], the refinement of the eutectic Mg₂Si phase is also important. After UT, the eutectic Mg₂Si phase changes from the coarse Chinese character to a fine dot shape, as shown in Fig. 5. These dot eutectic Mg₂Si phases with the size of less than 1 μ m can serve as strong obstacles to the dislocation movement, leading to strength enhancement. In addition, the SiC_{np} and Mg₂Si phase have lower coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) than the matrix alloy, resulting in the formation of residual plastic strain between the reinforcement phases and the matrix after solidification, which helps generate dislocations at the interface between the reinforcement phases and matrix to accommodate CTE mismatch [16]. Therefore, the mechanical properties of Mg₂Si+SiC_{np}/Al-Cu composites with UT are significantly improved.

Table 2: Comparison of the mechanical properties of matrix alloy and different composites.

Materials	States	UTS (MPa)	Elongation (%)
10%Mg ₂ Si+1%SiC/Al-Cu Composites	Without UT	286 \pm 10	1.3 \pm 0.3
10%Mg ₂ Si+1%SiC/Al-Cu Composites	With UT	336 \pm 8	3.0 \pm 0.3
Al-Cu matrix alloy	With UT	260 \pm 10	10.5 \pm 1
1%SiC/Al-Cu Composites	With UT	272 \pm 10	12.5 \pm 1

4 CONCLUSIONS

- (1) After UT, the eutectic Mg₂Si phase is remarkably refined from coarse Chinese characters to fine strips or dots and uniformly distributed in the composites, and the primary α -Al grains are also refined.
- (2) After UT, the SiC_{np} agglomerations are eliminated and SiC_{np} are uniformly distributed in the composites. The SiC_{np} can act as heterogeneous nucleus of Mg₂Si phase, or be captured by the Mg₂Si solid front during solidification, leading to the refinement of eutectic Mg₂Si phase.
- (3) After UT, the UTS and elongation of hybrid Mg₂Si+SiC_{np}/Al-Cu composites are 336 MPa and 3.0%, respectively, which are increased by 31.3% and 130.8%, compared with the composites without UT. The UTS of the hybrid Mg₂Si+SiC_{np}/Al-Cu composites is also 33.5% higher than that

of Al-Cu matrix alloy and 23.5% higher than that of 1wt.% SiC_{np}/Al-Cu composites prepared by the same process.

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